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Demographic Characteristics and Cervical Epithelial Abnormalities among Women Evaluated at a Cervical Cancer Screening Programme in Jos, North-Central Nigeria: A Cross-Sectional Study

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ABSTRACT

Cervical cancer remains a major public health challenge in low- and middle-income countries, where limited access to organised screening contributes to delayed detection. This study described the demographic and reproductive characteristics of women evaluated at a cervical cancer screening programme in Jos, North-Central Nigeria, determined the distribution of cervical cytological abnormalities and assessed associated factors. A cross-sectional study was conducted among 101 women aged 25–84 years at Jos University Teaching Hospital between October 2019 and April 2020. Sociodemographic and reproductive characteristics were obtained using a structured questionnaire. Cervical cytology was evaluated using Pap smear and reported according to the 2014 Bethesda System, while cervical carcinoma cases were histologically confirmed. Associations were assessed using the chi-square test, with significance set at $p < 0.05$. Using the 2014 Bethesda System for Reporting Cervical Cytology, 29.7% of participants had normal cytology, while cytological abnormalities comprised ASC-US (14.9%), LSIL (14.9%), ASC-H (9.9%), and HSIL (14.9%); histologically confirmed cervical carcinoma accounted for 15.8%. Age ($p = 0.0001$) and history of oestrogen exposure ($p = 0.030$) showed significant associations with cervical epithelial abnormality category. These findings highlight the importance of sustained cervical cancer screening, particularly among older women.

Keywords: Cervical epithelial abnormalities; Demographic factors; Pap smear; Cervical cancer; Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Cervical cancer remains a major public health challenge and one of the leading causes of cancer-related morbidity and mortality among women worldwide, with the greatest burden occurring in low- and middle-income countries (Arbyn *et al.*, 2020; World Health Organization [WHO], 2024). Despite being largely preventable through effective screening, early detection, and treatment of precursor lesions, many women in resource-limited settings continue to present with advanced disease due to inadequate screening coverage and limited access to preventive healthcare services. Persistent infection with high-risk human papillomavirus (HPV) is recognised as the principal cause of cervical cancer development (Schiffman *et al.*, 2016; WHO, 2024). However, progression from HPV infection to cervical intraepithelial lesions and invasive carcinoma is influenced by several demographic, reproductive, and behavioural factors. Factors such as increasing age, high parity, early age at sexual debut, and history of sexually transmitted infections have been reported to influence the occurrence and pattern of cervical epithelial abnormalities (Muñoz *et al.*, 2002; Nessa *et al.*, 2020). Cervical cytology using the Papanicolaou (Pap) smear has played a central role in cervical cancer prevention programmes by enabling the detection of premalignant epithelial changes before progression to invasive cancer (Nayar & Wilbur, 2015; Pangarkar, 2022). Cytological interpretation using standardised reporting systems, such as the Bethesda System, allows classification of cervical abnormalities into clinically relevant categories, including atypical squamous cells of undetermined significance (ASC-US), low-grade squamous intraepithelial lesion (LSIL), atypical squamous cells cannot exclude high-grade squamous intraepithelial lesion (ASC-H), and high-grade squamous intraepithelial lesion (HSIL) (Pangarkar, 2022). In Nigeria, cervical cancer remains an important public health concern despite the availability of screening services in some healthcare institutions. Although studies have reported cervical cytology patterns in different regions of the country (Okunowo *et al.*, 2023; Offor *et al.*, 2025), differences in demographic profiles, reproductive characteristics, and healthcare utilisation emphasise the need for region-specific data to guide cervical cancer prevention strategies. Therefore, this study aimed to describe the demographic and reproductive characteristics of women evaluated at a cervical cancer screening programme in Jos, North-Central Nigeria. It also determined the distribution of cervical cytological abnormalities and histologically confirmed cervical cancer cases, and assessed demographic and reproductive factors associated with cervical epithelial abnormalities.

METHODS

Study Design and Setting

This was a cross-sectional study conducted at Jos University Teaching Hospital (JUTH), Jos, Plateau State, North-Central Nigeria, between October 2019 and April 2020. JUTH is a tertiary healthcare institution that provides specialist services and serves as a referral centre for Plateau State and neighbouring regions. The study was carried out at the Operation Stop Cervical Cancer Unit of the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, which provides cervical cancer screening services using Papanicolaou (Pap) smear, visual inspection with acetic acid, and colposcopy.

Study Population

The study population comprised women who presented for cervical cancer screening at the Operation Stop Cervical Cancer Unit, Jos University Teaching Hospital (JUTH). Cervical samples were obtained for Papanicolaou (Pap) smear evaluation, and participants were categorised based on cytological findings according to the 2014 Bethesda System for Reporting Cervical Cytology. Cervical cancer cases confirmed by histopathological examination of cervical biopsy specimens were also included. The study included non-pregnant women aged 18–84 years who provided informed consent. Women with previous treatment for cervical premalignant lesions or invasive cervical cancer, previous hysterectomy, prior cervical surgical procedures, or other co-existing malignancies were excluded.

Sampling Technique and Participant Recruitment

Participants were recruited using a systematic sampling technique among eligible women presenting for cervical cancer screening during the study period. Eligible women who met the inclusion criteria were approached, and written informed consent was obtained before enrolment. Demographic and reproductive information was collected using a structured questionnaire, after which cervical samples were obtained for Pap smear evaluation. Participants with clinically suspected cervical cancer were recruited from the gynaecological oncology unit. Cervical cancer diagnosis was confirmed through histopathological examination of cervical biopsy specimens. A total of 101 women were included in the final analysis.

Data Collection

Participant information was obtained using an interviewer-administered structured questionnaire. Data collected included sociodemographic characteristics, reproductive history, and clinical and lifestyle factors including age, educational status, marital status, parity, history of abortion, age at first delivery, age at first sexual intercourse, history of sexually transmitted infection, oestrogen exposure, alcohol consumption, and body mass index.

Cervical Cytology and Histological Evaluation

Cervical samples were collected from the transformation zone using standard procedures and processed using the Papanicolaou staining technique. Microscopic evaluation was performed with the assistance of a certified cytopathologist. Cytological findings were reported according to the 2014 Bethesda System and categorised as normal cytology, ASC-US, LSIL, ASC-H, or HSIL. Women with clinically suspected cervical cancer underwent colposcopy-directed cervical biopsy performed by a gynaecological oncologist. Biopsy specimens were processed and examined by a histopathologist, and only histologically confirmed cervical carcinoma cases were included in the cervical cancer category.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analysed using STATA version 17.0. Categorical variables were summarised using frequencies and percentages. Associations between demographic and reproductive variables and cervical epithelial abnormality categories were assessed using the chi-square test. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee of Jos University Teaching Hospital (JUTH/DCS/ADM/XXVIII/1264). Written informed consent was obtained from all participants before enrolment, and confidentiality of participant information was maintained throughout the study.

RESULTS

Demographic and Reproductive Characteristics of the Study Population

A total of 101 women aged 25–84 years were included in the study. The largest proportion of participants were within the age groups 55–64 years (30.7%) and 35–44 years (28.7%). More than half of the participants had tertiary education (52.5%), followed by primary (23.8%) and secondary education (22.8%), while only 1.0% had no formal education. Most participants were married (75.2%). Regarding reproductive characteristics, 55.4% of participants had five or more deliveries, with 49.5% having a parity of 5–9 and 5.9% having a parity of 10–14. A history of at least one previous abortion was reported by 73.3% of participants. The most common age at first delivery was 20–24 years (35.6%), followed by 25–29 years (25.7%). Most women reported first sexual intercourse between 20–24 years (44.0%) and 15–19 years (40.0%). A history of sexually transmitted infection was reported by 33.7% of participants, while 40.6% reported previous oestrogen exposure. Most participants had a healthy body mass index (54.5%) (Table 1).

Distribution of Cervical Cytological Categories and Histologically Confirmed Cervical Cancer Cases

Among the 101 participants, 30 (29.7%) had normal cervical cytology based on Pap smear evaluation. Abnormal cervical cytological findings classified according to the 2014 Bethesda System were observed in 55 participants (54.5%), comprising ASC-US in 15 (14.9%), LSIL in 15 (14.9%), ASC-H in 10 (9.9%), and HSIL in 15 (14.9%). Histologically confirmed cervical carcinoma accounted for 16 cases (15.8%) (Table 2; Figure 1).

Association Between Demographic Factors and Cervical Epithelial Abnormalities

The association between demographic and reproductive variables and cervical epithelial abnormality categories is shown in Table 3. Age demonstrated a statistically significant association with cervical epithelial abnormality category ($p = 0.0001$). Normal cytology was more frequently observed among younger women, particularly those aged 25–34 years (71.4%), whereas older age groups demonstrated greater proportions of high-grade lesions and carcinoma. HSIL was most frequent among women aged 55–64 years, while cervical carcinoma was observed more frequently with advancing age (Figure 2). History of oestrogen exposure was also significantly associated with cervical epithelial abnormality category ($p = 0.030$). Women without previous oestrogen exposure had higher proportions of HSIL and cervical carcinoma compared with those who reported previous exposure (Figure 3). Other demographic and reproductive variables, including educational status ($p = 0.398$), marital status ($p = 0.761$), history of abortion ($p = 0.939$), age at first delivery ($p = 0.678$), age at first sexual intercourse ($p = 0.726$), history of sexually transmitted infection ($p = 0.373$), parity ($p = 0.120$), alcohol consumption ($p = 0.096$), and body mass index ($p = 0.092$), were not significantly associated with cervical epithelial abnormality category (Table 3).

Table 1. Demographic and Reproductive Characteristics of the Study Participants (N=101)

Variable	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Age Group (Years)		
25 – 34	7	6.9
35 – 44	29	28.7
45 – 54	25	24.8
55 – 64	30	29.7
65 – 74	9	7.9
75 – 84	1	1.0
Educational Status		
None	1	1.0
Primary	24	23.8
Secondary	23	22.8
Tertiary	53	52.5
Marital Status		
Single	9	8.9
Married	75	74.2
Separated	4	4.0
Widow	11	10.9
Divorced	2	2.0
Parity		
< 5	45	44.6
5 – 9	50	49.5
10 – 14	6	5.9
History of Previous Abortion		
NONE	27	26.7
1	39	38.6
≥ 2	35	34.7
Age at First Delivery (Years)		
15 – 19	23	22.8
20 – 24	36	35.6
25 – 29	26	25.7
≥ 30	16	15.8

Variable	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Age at First Sexual Intercourse		
10 – 14	2	2.0
15 – 19	40	40.0
20 – 24	44	44.0
≥25	15	15.0

History of Sexually Transmitted Disease		
No	67	66.3
Yes	34	33.7
History of Oestrogen		
No	60	59.4
Yes	41	40.6
Alcohol Consumption		
No	88	87.1
Yes	13	12.9
Body Mass Index		
Underweight	14	13.8
Healthy Weight	57	56.4
Overweight	25	24.8
Obesity	5	5.0

Table 2: Distribution of Cervical Cytological Categories and Histologically Confirmed Cervical Carcinoma Among Study Participants (N=101)

Diagnostic Category	Frequency	Percentage
Normal Cytology	30	29.7
ASC-US	15	14.9
LSIL	15	14.9
ASC-H	10	9.9
HSIL	15	14.9
CaCx	16	15.8
Total	101	100

ASC-US: atypical squamous cells of undetermined significance; LSIL: low-grade squamous intraepithelial lesion; ASC-H: atypical squamous cells—cannot exclude high-grade squamous intraepithelial lesion; HSIL: high-grade squamous intraepithelial lesion.

Table 3. Association between demographic and reproductive characteristics and cervical epithelial abnormality categories

Variable	Cervical Cytology Outcome						p-value
	Normal	ASC-US	ASC-H	LSIL	HSIL	CaCx	
	N=30 (%)	N=15 (%)	N=10 (%)	N=15 (%)	N=15 (%)	N=16 (%)	
Educational Status							
None	1(100.00)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	0.398
Primary	4(16.67)	2(8.33)	2(8.33)	4(16.67)	5(20.83)	7(29.17)	
Secondary	9(39.13)	2(8.70)	2(8.70)	6(26.09)	4(17.39)	0(0.00)	
Tertiary	16(30.19)	11(20.75)	6(11.32)	5(9.43)	6(11.32)	9(16.98)	
Marital Status							
Single	0(0.00)	1(11.11)	2(22.22)	1(11.11)	3(33.33)	2(22.22)	0.150
Married	29(38.67)	10(13.33)	7(9.33)	12(16.00)	7(9.33)	10(13.33)	
Separated	0(0.00)	2(50.00)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	1(25.00)	1(25.00)	
Widow	1(9.09)	2(18.18)	1(9.09)	1(9.09)	4(36.36)	2(18.18)	
Divorced	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	1(50.00)	0(0.00)	1(50.00)	
Age Group (Years)							
18 – 24	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	0.0001
25 – 34	5(71.43)	1(14.29)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	1(14.29)	0(0.00)	
35 – 44	15(51.72)	5(17.24)	2(6.90)	4(13.79)	2(6.90)	1(3.45)	
45 – 54	7(28.00)	4(16.00)	3(12.00)	4(16.00)	2(8.00)	5(20.00)	
55 – 64	2(6.67)	5(16.67)	3(10.00)	7(23.33)	8(26.67)	5(16.67)	
65 – 74	1(11.11)	0(0.00)	2(22.22)	0(0.00)	1(11.11)	5(55.56)	
75 – 84	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	1(100.00)	
Age at first Coitus (Years)							
10 – 14	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	1(100.00)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	0.726
15 – 19	12(29.27)	5(12.20)	3(7.32)	6(14.63)	7(17.07)	8(19.51)	
20 – 24	12(27.91)	7(16.28)	6(13.95)	7(16.28)	5(11.63)	6(13.95)	
25 – 29	4(33.33)	3(25.00)	1(8.33)	1(8.33)	2(16.67)	4(33.33)	
30 – 34	0(0.00)	1(20.00)	1(20.00)	1(20.00)	2(30.00)	2(30.00)	
History of Sexually Transmitted Disease							
No	23(32.86)	12(17.14)	7(10.00)	8(11.43)	8(11.43)	12(17.14)	0.373
Yes	7(22.58)	3(9.68)	3(9.68)	7(22.58)	7(22.58)	4(12.90)	
Parity							
Less Than 5	15(33.33)	8(17.78)	3(6.67)	5(11.11)	4(8.89)	10(22.22)	0.120
5 – 9	14(28.00)	7(14.00)	6(12.00)	9(18.00)	8(16.00)	6(12.00)	
10 – 14	1(16.67)	0(0.00)	1(16.67)	1(16.67)	3(50.00)	0(0.00)	
Variable							
Variable	Cervical Cytology Outcome						p-value
	Normal	ASC-US	ASC-H	LSIL	HSIL	CaCx	
	N=30 (%)	N=15 (%)	N=10 (%)	N=15 (%)	N=15 (%)	N=16 (%)	
History of Oestrogen							
No	14(23.33)	6(10.00)	6(10.00)	8(13.33)	12(20.00)	14(23.33)	0.030
Yes	16(39.02)	9(21.95)	4(9.76)	7(17.07)	3(7.32)	2(4.88)	
Body Mass Index							
Underweight	7(50.00)	0(0.00)	2(14.92)	1(7.14)	3(21.43)	1(7.14)	0.090
Healthy Weight	13(22.80)	11(19.30)	7(12.28)	9(15.79)	11(19.30)	6(10.53)	
Overweight	8(32.00)	4(16.00)	1(4.00)	5(20.00)	1(4.00)	6(24.00)	
Obesity	2(40.00)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	3(60.00)	

Figure 1. Distribution of Cervical Cytological Categories and Histologically Confirmed Cervical Carcinoma

Figure 2. Distribution of Cervical Epithelial Abnormalities According to Age Group

Figure 3. Relationship Between Oestrogen Exposure and Cervical Epithelial Abnormalities

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study evaluated the demographic and reproductive characteristics, distribution of cervical epithelial abnormalities, and associated factors among women assessed at a cervical cancer screening programme in Jos, North-Central Nigeria. Cervical epithelial abnormalities occurred across different demographic groups, with age and history of oestrogen exposure demonstrating significant associations with cervical epithelial abnormality categories. The majority of participants were within the middle and older age groups, particularly those aged 35–64 years. This aligned with previous reports that the burden of high-grade cervical lesions and invasive cervical cancer is concentrated among middle-aged and older women due to cumulative exposure to high-risk HPV, immunosenescence, and delays in accessing screening or treatment (Arbyn *et al.*, 2020; Bray *et al.*, 2018; Schiffman *et al.*, 2016). More than half of the participants had tertiary education, and most were married. The relatively high educational attainment may reflect the hospital-based nature of the screening programme, as women with higher educational status may have greater awareness of cervical cancer prevention and better access to screening services (Okunowo *et al.*, 2023; Saaka & Hambali, 2024). However, educational status was not significantly associated with cervical epithelial abnormality categories, suggesting that although education may influence screening behaviour, development of cervical abnormalities is influenced by multiple biological and reproductive factors (Muñoz *et al.*, 2002; Nessa *et al.*, 2020). Normal cytology was more frequently observed among younger women, whereas high-grade lesions and cervical carcinoma occurred predominantly among older women. This supports the established progression of persistent oncogenic HPV infection to high-grade lesions and invasive cervical carcinoma over time (Schiffman *et al.*, 2016; World Health Organization, 2024). Although parity was not significantly associated with cervical epithelial abnormality categories, women with very high parity demonstrated a greater proportion of HSIL. High parity has been described as a potential cofactor in cervical carcinogenesis, possibly through hormonal influences, cervical trauma related to childbirth, and increased susceptibility of the cervical transformation zone (Muñoz *et al.*, 2002). Although age at first sexual intercourse was not significantly associated with cervical epithelial abnormalities in this study, early sexual debut remains an established factor associated with increased exposure to HPV infection and cervical dysplasia in previous studies (Manga *et al.*, 2015; Mbamara &

Ikpeze, 2011). History of oestrogen exposure was significantly associated with cervical epithelial abnormality categories. Women without a history of oestrogen exposure had higher proportions of HSIL and cervical carcinoma, while those with prior oestrogen use were more frequently represented in the normal cytology group. However, existing literature is mixed; some studies have implicated long-term oestrogen exposure, particularly through oral contraceptives, in HPV persistence and cervical carcinogenesis (Appleby et al., 2007; Moreno et al., 2002), while others have reported no consistent association (Ajah et al., 2015; Anastasiou et al., 2022). The differences in findings may be related to duration of exposure, type of hormonal preparation, population characteristics, and confounding factors such as parity and sexual behaviour. Other variables including marital status, parity, body mass index, history of sexually transmitted infections, and abortion history were not significantly associated with cervical epithelial abnormality categories. Although these factors have been reported in some studies, persistent high-risk HPV infection remains the principal determinant of cervical carcinogenesis. This study provides important information on demographic characteristics and cervical epithelial abnormalities among women evaluated at a cervical cancer screening programme in North-Central Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated variations in cervical epithelial abnormalities across different demographic and reproductive groups among women evaluated at a cervical cancer screening programme in Jos, North-Central Nigeria. High-grade cervical lesions and histologically confirmed cervical carcinoma were observed more frequently among older women, with age showing a significant association with cervical epithelial abnormality category. History of oestrogen exposure was also significantly associated with cervical epithelial abnormalities, although this finding requires further investigation. Other demographic and reproductive characteristics were not significantly associated with cervical epithelial abnormalities in this study. These findings emphasise the importance of sustained cervical cancer screening among eligible women to improve early detection of high-grade lesions and invasive disease.

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